

EFFECTIVENESS OF BOARD STRUCTURE MODELS AND FIRM'S PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM PAKISTAN'S TEXTILE SECTOR

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Abstract

The study intends to identify the factors influencing corporate governance of textile firms in Pakistan, as the textile sector is fundamental role perform in Pakistan economy. Consequently, it is essential to explore the intricacies of corporate governance within the textile sector to enhance its performance. The research employs panel data from 99 companies that are listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange, over the years 2007 to 2022, with published financial reports from the textile sector. The researcher uses the system GMM variables like profit instead of ROA, governance performance taken as CEO experience, firm efficiencies consider a stock return in regression method for analysis. This method is employed when encountering heteroskedasticity of an indeterminate kind, utilising the Generalised Method of Moments (GMM). GMM leverages orthogonality criteria to facilitate efficient estimate amid heteroskedasticity of uncertain shape. The research examines the influence of corporate governance on the success of textile firms. The return on assets functions as an indicator of company performance, whereas the market value of stocks and the age of the firm are used as measures of firm size and complexity; these variables were utilised to examine corporate governance. The study revealed that company performance favourably influences stock returns, return on assets, and firm size, but leverage and corporate governance have negative impacts.

Introduction

The textile industry employs almost 25 million people and accounts for 8.5% of Pakistan's GDP. From raw resources to final goods, Pakistan's textile sector has a full value chain. Its significance and global reach are demonstrated by Pakistan's ranking as Asia's eighth-largest exporter of textile materials. The concentration of the textile industry is largest in Faisalabad (28 percent) and Karachi (38 percent). 116 of the 464 textile operations are based in Sindh, while 316 are in Punjab (PBIT report for Pakistan's textile sector, August 2018). According to PBS data for FY2024 (fiscal year

2023-24), Pakistan's textile group exports increased by around 0.93% during fiscal year 2023-24, reaching \$16.655 billion compared to \$16.501 billion in the preceding fiscal year (2022-23). The textile exports surged due to several government incentives that helped exporters overcome the challenges caused by COVID-19 and disruptions in the supply chain. Pakistan was able to get orders that had been diverted from countries with stricter shutdown standards because the government decided to keep the economy running during lockdowns. An explosion in the export of textiles with added value

has been the primary driver of this growth over the past five years. Compared to \$2.34 billion in the same month a year ago, export sales fell 5.17 percent to \$2.21 billion, according to PBS statistics. A negative trend in the export sector was indicated by a 23.95% month-over-month fall in export earnings, which stands in stark contrast to the volumetric gain in exports seen the previous month IFC. (2022, May 27)

The textile industry in Pakistan is the largest and most vital among the country's 12 non-financial economic sectors, with a total of 411 firms. It represents a substantial 40% of Pakistan's total non-financial industry, consisting of 164 textile companies. Due to the unavailability of certain information from the remaining organisations, the researcher utilised financial data from 99 textile manufacturers. The financial success of the textile sector significantly influences the performance of other industries. The primary responsibility of a financial manager is to enhance shareholder wealth and increase the worth of the business, which is achievable through greater financial performance.

This research aims to discover the principal elements that influence a firm's financial performance. Prior research consistently shows that many elements substantially influence a firm's overall success. In 1952, numerous ideas were offered, with David Durand initiating talks on company value. To substantiate his argument, he formulated three theories: the Net Income (NI) technique, the Net Operating Income (NOI) method, and the conventional perspective.

As per the following theories and prior research Durand (1952) contended that heightened leverage might improve business performance; however, David D. struggled to furnish practical rationale to substantiate this assertion. Modigliani (1958) contested the idea that a firm's performance is exclusively reliant on its leverage utilisation. The notion of arbitrage was presented, elucidating how investors capitalise on pricing discrepancies across several marketplaces. This approach entails investors acquiring shares or making investments at minimal costs, which they subsequently sell for favourable prices across many marketplaces.

In 1963, Modigliani and Miller demonstrated that debt provides a tax shield advantage via interest

deduction. Their analysis highlighted that a firm's worth is not intrinsically linked to its leverage position.

Subsequent research has repeatedly demonstrated that business financial success is affected by several factors. A research focused on Jordan's non-financial sector was conducted by Zeitun and Tian (1997). A number of factors were investigated in relation to business success, including growth, risk management, size, tax policy and leverage and asset tangibility. The subsequent part examines the literature from prior studies to furnish theoretical and empirical backing for this investigation. Subsequently, the following sections will address methodology, data analysis, and conclusion, each to be examined individually. The next is Literature view, thereafter methodology then result discussion and finally conclusion and policy implications at last references

Literature Review

Rostami et al. (2015) examine the robust and positive link among CEO duality, ownership concentration, board independence, CEO tenure, and return on assets (ROA). In contrast, a substantial negative link exists between institutional ownership, board size, and Return on Assets. Moreover, a significant and substantive association exists among institutional ownership, board independence, CEO duality, CEO longevity, and stock return. Conversely, a significant negative link exists between ownership concentration and board size concerning stock returns. Sukesti et al. (2021) examined potential factors including work experience, executive leadership, research on job performance and the succession of chief executive officers.

The findings revealed a detrimental correlation between Post-Succession Firm Performance and the preceding CEO. The findings of Sukesti et al. (2021) were consistent with those of Koyuncu (2014) and Rostami et al. (2015). Koyuncu and Hamori (2014) examined the possible influence of senior executive experience on a firm's financial performance. Corporations to assess the correlation. The researchers examined potential variables including work experience, executive leadership, job performance, and CEO succession for this study. The results demonstrated a

detrimental relationship between the performance of the firm following succession and the previous CEO's influence. The results demonstrated an inverse relationship between the performance of the firm following succession and the previous CEO's impact.

In 1992, Smith and Watts collaborated on a study examining the relationship between investment opportunity sets and various aspects of business finance, including dividend and compensation practices. A variety of empirical relationships were analysed regarding the connections between corporate policy actions and the attributes of businesses. The authors examined dividends, corporate finance, executive remuneration practices, regulation, investment opportunity set, and company size utilising time series, cross-sectional, and regression analyses. The analysis revealed a positive relationship among contracting theories when examined alongside dividend, compensation, and financial policies. Roy (2014) conducted an analysis of corporate governance and its impact on the performance of publicly traded enterprises in India. The connection between robust Corporate Governance practices and a company's overall performance. The author utilises audit considerations, board committees, directors, capital structure attributes, and ownership, alongside other defined control factors, that are associated with the Market Book Value Ratio and Return on Assets, which act as measures of a firm's performance. Knight and Weir (2009) performed a panel data analysis focussing on the expenses, corporate governance practices, and ownership structures of large publicly listed companies in the UK. The researcher utilised the sales to total assets ratio, growth potential, and free cash flows as indicators for agency costs. The obtained data was analysed using Tobit regression, instrumental variables, and fixed effects. The findings indicated that alterations in board arrangements often do not influence agency expenses. Researchers made further enquiries concerning the information communicated to shareholders during the adoption of the proposed governance framework. Maug (1997) concluded that both amicable and antagonistic takeovers exhibit little costs and limited restructuring possibilities. Both external

acquisitions and aggressive takeovers possess cheap expenses and significant restructuring possibilities. The internal takeover possesses little restructuring potential but incurs substantial costs. Yang et al. (2008) conducted a theoretical investigation revealing that board structure correlates with organizational size. Researchers also determined that smaller organisations often had more autonomous boards. Likewise, companies exhibiting significant volatility typically had smaller and less autonomous boards. Zhao et al. (2009) conducted a time series study on factors influencing the size and makeup of corporate boards in the United States. The most significant factors observed were business size, merger activity, growth potential, and regional expansion. Findings indicated no significant association between board size and business success.

Lehn & Poulsen (1989) identify the primary sources of free cash flows in the context of a corporation becoming private as the mitigation of agency difficulties, tax savings, asymmetric knowledge, and redistribution from bondholders. Research indicates that a primary factor driving these improvements is the reduction of agency issues related to free cash flows, and that the probability of an organisation transitioning to private ownership is closely correlated with the ratio of unallocated cash flows.

Harris and Raviv (2006) found that the majority of the public favoured management control over aggressive takeovers. Moreover, hostile takeovers diminish the entity's worth. Likewise, the authors calculated that increased agency expenses correlate with a more rapid control of hostile takeovers. Hersch et al. (2004) originally quantified the proportion of women on boards to subsequently assess the influence of gender diversity on corporate governance. Research indicates a progressive 200% rise in the representation of women on corporate boards from 1990 to 1999. Moreover, researchers determined from the data that the probability of a woman being appointed to a corporate board with an existing female member is unfavourable. Tai (2024) evaluated the influence of corporate governance frameworks on company performance in China. The research was carried out utilising secondary data. Recent studies have demonstrated a substantial correlation

between various governance approaches and organisational effectiveness. Nevertheless, the academics have not produced a comprehensive analysis of the impact of different governance elements on organisational effectiveness. Yunusov (2024) evaluated the impact of corporate governance on organisational performance and financial stability. A comprehensive literature assessment was conducted using keywords to identify gaps and highlight strategies for improving productivity and financial stability in the global business landscape through effective corporate governance standards. Corporate governance significantly enhances financial stability by implementing effective supervision, governance systems, and risk management techniques.

Dazai et al. (2024) investigated the relationship between corporate governance and business performance within Japanese-listed family enterprises. The data collected from organisations with management ownership and Japanese listed corporations allowed the researchers to distinguish the effects of each ownership type on organisational performance. Regression analysis was performed to assess the hypotheses. Research indicates that family ownership below 5% in a management-led company structure is more successful than family-led management, unless ownership exceeds 20%. The empirical analysis demonstrates that management incentives effectively enhance a firm's performance, even in the absence of strong shareholder oversight.

Agency theory posits that in modern organisations with widespread ownership, management's actions may diverge from the objective of maximising shareholder profits, as initially proposed by Ross in 1973. In 1976, Jensen and Meckling defined the agency relationship as a contractual arrangement in which one or more individuals (the principals) appoint another individual (the agent) to perform tasks on their behalf, potentially including specific decision-making responsibilities. This situation may sometimes lead management to prioritise their interests above those of the shareholders. Therefore, the corporation requires assurances that management will act in the best interest of the owners. Hill and Jones (1992) expanded on agency theory by

asserting that principals and agents possess differing interests. It was suggested that principals could align these interests by offering suitable incentives to agents and covering monitoring expenses, thereby preventing self-serving behaviours. In 1985, Williamson posited that the protection of shareholder interests occurs when management's incentives align with those of shareholders, achieved through carefully designed compensation programs.

Firm Performance

Firm performance is simply an evaluation of the effectiveness of all strategies employed to meet corporate objectives, as noted by Yildiz and Caracas in 2012. In 1986, Venkatraman and Ramanujam classified corporate performance into three distinct domains, which include the effectiveness of financial and operational activities, along with the overall efficiency of the organisation.

Firm Performance (ROA) indicates the efficient utilisation of company assets to produce returns. Chandra et al. (2019) Wijayanto (2010) defines ROA as the ratio that reflects the profitability generated by a company's assets.

According to Murhadi (2015), ROA indicates the financial return generated from invested assets.

Haryanto (2016) Indicated that a four-star profitability rating signifies the firm's strong earning power and effective utilisation of its assets to create profit.

Watiningsih, (2018) Assert that if the company's situation is favourable and it generates sufficient profit, its capital structure will diminish, negating the necessity for substantial debt; the retained earnings are adequate for utilisation, reflecting a preference for less debt. According to Akhtar et al. (2011), the business's return on assets (ROA) is elevated, signifying that the company occupies a superior level of profitability.

Effect of Stock return on company performance

The firms grow due to their elevated stock prices and appealing share returns, which attract investors, alongside the overall worth of the company. According to Laksitaputri (2012), it also instills confidence in the firm. In an Efficient

Capital Market, the share price incorporates all relevant information and market movements based on stock returns, as well as fundamental and technical factors that impact stock prices. Investors determine value based on firm stock prices, while other criteria are utilised to predict these values. The trade prices of stocks will influence an investor's mindset and foster an optimistic outlook.

Larger organisations typically own a substantial amount of assets, attracting investor interest due to the perception that their management is more competent and capable of efficient profit generation. Ha and Minh (2018) contended that the firm's value and size exhibit a significant and positive correlation, with the trust of investors being bolstered by the increase in the company's worth and its stock prices.

A high return on assets signifies that a company is effectively utilising its assets. Furthermore, it demonstrates the degree to which the organisation may optimise revenues through the utilisation of its assets. The net income to total assets ratio is a method to quantify it. A high return on assets indicates that the company's resources are being effectively utilised to create money. A rise in income influences stock prices as it signifies enhanced profits for investors. According to Daeli (2018) and Ng et al. (2020), a higher return on assets (ROA) influenced stock performance. Return on assets (ROA) exerts a favourable influence on stock returns.

Chief Executive Officer Experience

The Chief Executive Officer, or CEO, is a professional who occupies a pivotal role inside the organisation, responsible for significant corporate decisions, overseeing operations, ensuring optimal resource allocation, and supervising financial and accounting affairs. Wegge et al. (2006) propose that appointing a CEO with multidimensional experience can significantly enhance firm performance and ensure attention to Corporate Board and R&D decisions. The CEO should possess a diverse array of professional experiences that contribute to the firm's advancement.

Furthermore, Jiang et al. (2015), Matsunaga and Yeung (1997), and Schrand and Zechman (2015) posited that CEOs with substantial work

experience are inclined to implement moderate accounting practices that emphasise earning patterns, along with more accurate forecasting techniques that facilitate the company's growth. Furthermore, a CEO possessing accounting expertise may effectively mitigate fraudulent activity within organisations. A CEO's significant experience improves the efficiency and effectiveness of business performance, since resource-dependent theory posits that experience has a progressive connection with firm performance. Erickson et al. (2003) posited that CEOs with industry expertise anticipate substantial financial compensation and incentives from the organisation. The incidence results in increased expense and, thus, a deterioration in corporate performance. Hamori and Koyuncu (2010) assert that an experienced CEO is negatively correlated with the firm's financial performance following succession. In summary, the job-specific capabilities of various businesses consistently result in a detrimental effect on performance.

Firm complexity

The two interrelated functions may be linked to the complexity of the firm. Linck et al. (2008). An effective board for a complex organisation should include external members with relevant skills, expertise, and influence across various domains. Large corporations characterised by complex operational and financial structures, or those with fully decentralised activities, tend to benefit more from external parties. This trend enhances the probability of board diversification and increased autonomy (Boone et al., 2007; Linck et al., 2008; Coles et al., 2008).

Fama and Jensen (1983) argue that while monitoring expenses rise with organisational complexity, the advantages of effective monitoring should surpass these costs.

Large corporations tend to have complex operational and financial structures, as well as decentralised operations. These companies may possess greater leverage. Business size and financial leverage serve as indicators of firm complexity (Fama and Jensen, 1983; Booth and Deli, 1999; Bushman et al., 2004; Linck et al., 2008). Boone et al. (2007) and Linck et al. (2008) suggested that

firm age acts as an indicator of firm complexity. Linck et al. (2008) suggested incorporating the square of company age into the regression models. Adams and Ferreira (2007) and Raheja (2005) argue that the amount of private rewards accessible to managers is positively associated with enhanced board oversight and increased board independence. Jensen (1986) employs free cash flow as an indicator of private benefits.

Advising and monitoring costs

It is superfluous for entire enterprises to benefit from external scrutiny and counsel. Jensen (1993) contends that extensive boards of directors supervising nascent firms incur more expenses. External directors on these corporations' boards may exacerbate the free-rider issue, as well as elevate remuneration and coordination expenses. Linck et al. (2008).

Moreover, it is costly for organisations with information asymmetries to transmit firm-specific, sensitive information to external parties. Maug, 1997. Fama R. and Jensen (1983) assert that companies exhibiting greater volatility in stock returns are more prone to harbour knowledge that is inaccessible to external parties. Consistent with Linck et al. (2008), the present study substitutes advising and monitoring expenses with the MTB ratio, research and development expenditure, and the monthly standard deviation of stock returns. Companies with higher research and development expenditures and market-to-book ratios are more likely to possess expansion opportunities. Smith et al. (1992) and Gaver et al. (1993). The present analysis use the standard deviation of stock returns as a proxy for information asymmetry, in accordance with Linck et al. (2008) and Fama et al. (1983).

Board size and independence are expected to diminish alongside these characteristics, as monitoring and advisory costs are forecasted to increase. Combining the roles of board chair and CEO increases the likelihood that growth-oriented organisations and those with significant information asymmetry will confer greater authority upon the CEO.

Hypothesis Development and Conceptual Framework

The primary responsibilities of the firm's governing body, the directors, include providing counsel and overseeing management operations. Raheja (2005); Adams et al. (2007).

Management oversight serves as a safeguard against fraudulent activities perpetrated by management. Linck et al. (2008). Advising involves providing guidance to the executive team and developing strategic business initiatives aimed at enhancing future growth and increasing the company's profitability.

The two positions are interdependent.

This includes understanding market dynamics and industry trends, involvement in strategic decision-making, awareness of insider information, and the techniques for obtaining such information, thereby aligning the board with management. Alignment may compromise the board's ability to critically evaluate management for indications of harmful behaviour. Each organisation will determine its board structure by assessing the potential costs and benefits of oversight, in conjunction with its economic characteristics. Linck et al. (2008). A universal board structure applicable to all firms does not exist.

H1: Leverage is expected to adversely affect firm performance.

H2: A significant relationship exists between corporate governance and firm performance.

H3: There is a relationship between stock returns and firm performance.

H4: Does firm size enhance performance?

H5: Can the performance of the firm depend on complexities?

Research Question

The primary aim of this study is to analyse the correlation between corporate governance in Pakistan's textile sector and the financial performance of individual companies.

This study investigates the correlation between business size and performance, the impact of corporate governance procedures on firm performance and shareholder expectations, and evaluates the effectiveness of corporate governance mechanisms.

Figure 01

Author illustration

Where Market-value of the equity is a proxy for size of the firm; Leverage is the logarithm of total liabilities divided by total assets; Return on Assets is calculated as the natural logarithm of earnings before interest and taxes divided by the total assets at the beginning of the year, which serves as a measure of firm performance. The firm's age is

defined as the period from its initial listing at the Pakistan Stocks Exchange (PSX) until the end of the fiscal year 2022. Additionally, the standard deviation of the monthly stock returns during the previous year is considered. CEO Experience is measured in years how many year experience of a person stays in textile sector.

Table 01: Variables Description, Types, Measure and Citation

Variable	Description	Type	Measure	Citation
CEO Experience	No of years in working as CEO position	Independent	Log of No of years in working as CEO position in textile sector	Mingxiang Lia,1, Pankaj C. Patelb,*,(2013)
Return on Assets	earnings before interest & taxes divided by beginning-of-year total assets (ROA is a proxy of firm performance);	Dependent	Log of NetIncome divided by TotalAssets	PAUL GOMPERS JOY ISHII ANDREW METRICK, (2003) James S. Lincka, (2008), Jeffrey M. Nettera, Tina Yangb (2007) Ishaku et al., (2019)
Firm Age	Listed year of the firm in Pak. Security Exchange Commission.	Independent	Log of firm age (complexities)	James S. Lincka, (2008), Jeffrey M. Nettera, Tina Yangb (2007)
Stock Return	percentage change in the price of a stock over a specific period	Independent	Standard deviation of (Current Share Price- Previous Share Price) whole divided by CSP.	Reza M. Monem, (2013) James S. Lincka, (2008), Jeffrey

				M. Nettera, Tina Yangb (2007)
Market-value of Equity	the Market-value of equity (taken as a firm's size);	Independent	Log of Current Market Price per Share multiply by Total No. of Outstanding Shares	Reza M. Monem, (2013) James S. Lincka, (2008), Jeffry M. Nettera, Tina Yangb (2007) Michael L. Lemmon and Karlv. (2003)
Leverage	Debt-to-assets ratio, show the percentage of company's assets that are debt financed.	Independent	Logarithm of total liabilities divided by total assets	Reza M. Monem, (2013) James S. Lincka, (2008), Jeffry M. Nettera, Tina Yangb (2007) MICHAEL L. LEMMON and KARLV. LINS(2003)

Data

The data source utilized in this study is a dynamic panel Dataset, derived from the annual publication report titled "Financial Statement Analysis of companies (non-financial)" listed in the Karachi Stock Exchange for the period 2007-2022" by the State Bank of Pakistan. Additionally, Stock price data are gathered from the Pakistan Stock Exchange. Furthermore, governance variables are to be taken from the company's prospectus available on their website.

Research Methodology

Econometric Regression Model

Arellano-Bover/Blundell-Bond Estimation (System GMM)

1. Arellano-Bover/Blundell-Bond Estimation employs System GMM methodology. Blundell and Bond (1998) and Arellano and Bover (1995) improved the System GMM estimator by advancing the foundational methodology. This method involves integrating level equations with first difference equations, using lagged differences as instruments for level equations and lagged levels for differenced equations
2. Levels Equation:

$$y_{it} = \alpha y_{it-1} + \beta X_{it} + \mu_i + \epsilon_{it}$$

(i)

Instruments: Lagged differences Δy_{it-s} , ΔX_{it-s} (e.g., Δy_{it-1} , Δy_{it-2} ,...) are used as instruments for the levels equation. These differences are uncorrelated with the individual effects μ_i/ϵ_{it}

3. First Differences Equation:

$$\Delta y_{it} = \alpha \Delta y_{it-1} + \beta \Delta X_{it} + \Delta \epsilon_{it}$$

(ii)

Instruments: Lagged levels (e.g., y_{it-2} , y_{it-3} ,...) are used as instruments for the differenced equation. These levels are uncorrelated with the differenced error term $\Delta \epsilon_{it}$

Prior studies indicate that endogeneity has arisen in the relationship between corporate governance and performance. This literature requires a thorough description and analysis. Ullah, Subhan et al. (2018) and Abdullah Chandi et al. (2017) argue that the lack of an explanatory factor may stem from endogeneity, linking the relationship of the variables to the residuals of the estimated model. Demsetz and Villalonga (2001) argued that reverse causality could be a factor contributing to the endogeneity between corporate governance and its performance indicators. The OLS estimate

coefficient in this context is biased and inconsistent because of the unobserved fixed effects related to the firm performance variable and the problem of endogeneity. Bhagat and Bolton (2008); Nguyen et al. (2015).

The implementation of a fixed-effect model for time-invariant variables serves as an effective strategy to address the issue of unobserved firm fixed effects. Consequently, the issue of endogeneity continues to be a concern among variables (Nguyen et al., 2015). Bhagat and Bolton (2008) utilised simultaneous equations, specifically applying 2-stage and 3-stage least squares to tackle endogeneity concerns. Cho (1998), Demsetz and Villalonga (2001), Nguyen et al. (2015), Iftikhar, K., & Azmat, S. (2024), and various other scholars support the Generalised Method of Moments (GMM), first proposed by Arellano and Bond in 1991. This method effectively addresses the endogeneity problem without the need for instrumental variables. Both 2-Stage Least Squares and 3-Stage Least Squares techniques may present challenges in classification. Wintoki, Linck, and Netter (2012). The AB GMM model was utilised to estimate the equation defining business performance as ROE (return on equity) Iftikhar, K., & Iftikhar, S. F. (2018).

The Arellano-Bover/Blundell-Bond Estimation utilises the GMM methodology for panel data analysis, selected for its suitability with the micro-panel dataset in our model, as GMM provides a robust approach for evaluating dynamic panel data models Iftikhar, K., & Iftikhar, S. F. (2018). Key econometric challenges, such as endogeneity, heteroscedasticity, and serial correlation, have been effectively addressed in the empirical study employing a panel technique. Dietrich and Wanzenried (2011) as well as Ozili (2017) support the use of the Generalised Method of Moments (G.M.M) to tackle challenges including variance, endogeneity, serial correlation, and multicollinearity, thereby ensuring the consistency of coefficients in statistical results. The AB/BB approach is gaining considerable attention in econometric theory related to dynamic panel datasets, as demonstrated by A. Ishaku et al. (2023), Iftikhar, K., & Azmat, S. (2024).

Model Specification

$$roa_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 mve_{it} + \beta_2 fa_{it} + \beta_3 lev_{it} + \beta_4 ce_{it} + \beta_5 Stdret_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

(iv)

MVE (Market Capitalization) represents the firm's size, LEV indicates the ratio of liabilities to assets, ROA (Profitability) assesses performance, ROA denotes the duration from the firm's initial listing on the Pakistan Stock Exchange to the conclusion of the 2022 fiscal year, and STDRET refers to the standard deviation of monthly stock returns from the preceding year. CEO experience is quantified in years.

Data Collection and Sampling Strategy

This study used a dynamic panel dataset obtained from the yearly report "Financial Statement Analysis of Non-Financial Companies" listed on the Karachi Stock Exchange for the period 2007-2022, published by the State Bank of Pakistan. Furthermore, stock price data is obtained from the Pakistan Stock Exchange. Additionally, governance variables will be sourced from the company's prospectus accessible on their website. The researcher chose the textile industry because of its significant representation in the non-financial sector and its contribution of 46% to GDP.

Panel data encompasses these unobserved heterogeneities, facilitating more precise evaluations of governance procedures. It acknowledges that not all textile firms adhere to identical governance frameworks.

The textile industry comprises several companies, suppliers, and manufacturers. Panel data effectively leverages information from identical textile entities throughout various time periods, minimising the necessity for large cross-sectional data acquisition. Researchers can examine governance methods across many organisations without beginning again each time.

Corporate governance strategies affect organisational performance, risk management, and sustainability. Panel data models include lagged effects, autocorrelations, and feedback loops related to governance acts. Researchers can assess the effectiveness of governance reforms, regulatory changes, and board processes over time for Dynamic Relationships and Policy Evaluation.

Effective corporate governance ensures compliance with legal requirements, ethical standards, and industry regulations. Panel data enables the oversight of governance practices related to risk evaluation, internal controls, and transparency. It provides insights into the risk management tactics utilised by textile firms and their adaption to changing business environments.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Analysis

The dataset comprises 1,574 observations concerning the return on assets for textile firms. The average return on assets for textile firms is approximately 2.27. The standard deviation of ROA is approximately 0.42, indicating a relatively low level of variability. The minimum ROA recorded is nearly zero (approximately -3.86e-16), suggesting that certain firms may experience minimal or negative returns. The maximum ROA is around 2.62, indicating that some firms exhibit outstanding performance. A total of 1,584 observations concerning stock returns for textile firms have been recorded. The average return on the stocks of these firms is approximately 1.81. The standard deviation of stock returns is approximately 0.15, suggesting a stable performance pattern. The minimum stock return recorded is around 1.04, whereas the maximum is about 1.87.

The dataset comprises 1,584 observations

concerning the experience of CEOs in textile firms. The average experience level of CEOs in these firms is approximately 1.51 years. The standard deviation of CEO experience is approximately 0.20, indicating a moderate level of variation. The observed minimum CEO experience is around 0.54, whereas the maximum is about 1.89.

A total of 1,584 observations pertain to the market value of equity for textile firms. The average market value of equity is approximately 9.25. The standard deviation of equity values is approximately 1.15, suggesting a degree of variability. It is important to observe that certain firms exhibit no equity value, whereas others attain a peak value of 11.12.

The dataset comprises 1,584 observations pertaining to leverage within textile firms. The average leverage ratio maintained by these firms is around 0.85. The standard deviation of leverage is approximately 0.15, indicating a degree of stability in financial structures. The observed minimum leverage is around 0.29, whereas the maximum reaches approximately 1.91.

A total of 1,584 observations pertain to the age of textile firms. These firms have, on average, been in existence for about 1.56 units of time, although the exact unit is not specified. The standard deviation of firm age is approximately 0.25, suggesting a degree of variability. The observed minimum firm age is around 0.48, whereas the maximum is about 3.31.

Table 02: Summary Statistics of full sample during the period from 2007-2022

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
Leverage	1574.	0.84883	0.14558	0.28676	1.90965
Profitability (ROA)	1574.	2.26972	0.4206	-3.85E-16	2.61767
Market Capitalization (MVE)	1584.	9.25191	1.14838	0	11.1174
Stock Return	1584.	1.81118	0.1455	1.01393	1.87039
Firm age	1584.	1.55721	0.24619	0.47121	3.30596
Ceo Experience	1584.	1.5123	0.2042	0.52434	2

Correlation Matrix

The dataset contains 1,574 items about the return on assets for textile companies. The mean return on assets for textile companies is around 2.27. The standard deviation of ROA is around 0.42,

signifying a very low degree of variability. The lowest reported ROA is practically zero (about -3.86e-16), indicating that certain enterprises may incur negligible or negative returns. The highest ROA is around 2.62, signifying that certain

businesses demonstrate exceptional performance. A total of 1,584 observations about stock returns for textile companies have been documented. The mean return on the equities of these companies is around 1.81. The standard deviation of stock returns is around 0.15, indicating a consistent performance trend. The least reported stock return is around 1.04, while the greatest is almost 1.87.

The dataset contains 1,584 observations about the experience of CEOs in textile companies. The mean tenure of CEOs in these companies is approximately 1.51 years. The standard deviation of CEO tenure is around 0.20, signifying a considerable degree of variability. The least CEO experience recorded is around 0.54, while the greatest is roughly 1.89.

There are 1,584 observations related to the market value of equity for textile companies. The mean market value of equities is around 9.25. The

standard deviation of equity values is around 1.15, indicating a level of unpredictability. It is noteworthy that some corporations own no equity value, while others reach a maximum value of 11.12.

The dataset contains 1,584 records related to leverage in textile companies. The typical leverage ratio upheld by these businesses is about 0.85. The mean deviation of leverage is around 0.15, signifying a level of stability in financial frameworks. The least observed leverage is roughly 0.29, while the greatest is about 1.91.

There are 1,584 observations on the age of textile enterprises. On average, these businesses have existed for around 1.56 time units, however the specific unit remains unspecified. The standard deviation of the firm's age is around 0.25, indicating a level of unpredictability. The smallest firm age found is around 0.48, while the maximum is at 3.31.

Table 03: Correlation Coefficient

	Profitability (ROA)	Stock Return	CEO Experience	Market Capitalization (MVE)	Leverage	Firm Age
Profitability (ROA)	1					
Stock Return	0.6650	1				
CEO Experience	-0.21505	-0.1108	1			
Market Capitalization (MVE)	0.10080	-0.06980	-0.03408	1		
Leverage	-0.46020	-0.25740	0.18080	-0.08805	1	
Firm Age	0.18130	0.12310	-0.15450	0.04360	-0.17401	1

Source Author Estimation

1.2 Empirical Results

This research examines 99 firms through unbalanced longitudinal data collection spanning from 2007 to 2022, yielding a total of 1,475 observations. The results demonstrate that the coefficient for stock return is 1.084, suggesting a robust positive correlation with firm performance. The coefficient for CEO Experience stands at -0.319, suggesting a negative correlation with firm performance. According to Erickson et al. (2003) and Hamori and Koyuncu (2010), the experience of a CEO within their industry is a strong predictor of significant financial rewards and incentives provided by the company. The occurrence leads to higher costs, which

subsequently results in a decrease in business performance. An experienced CEO shows a negative correlation with the firm's financial performance after succession. In conclusion, the specialised skills of different companies consistently lead to adverse effects on performance. The coefficient for market value of equity, which serves as an indicator of firm size, is 0.041, suggesting a positive correlation with firm performance. Research by Akhtar et al. (2011), Chandra et al. (2019), and Murhadi (2015) indicates that firms with high profitability are efficiently leveraging their assets to produce earnings. Daeli (2018) and Ng et al. (2020) provided evidence that a higher return on assets

(ROA) has a beneficial impact on a company's share performance. The leverage coefficient stands at -0.498, suggesting an inverse correlation with the firm's performance. The coefficient for firm age, used as a proxy variable for complexities, is 0.276, indicating that complexities correlate positively with firm performance. The link

between firm performance and complexities is shaped by various internal and external factors. An organisation that effectively manages complexities, adjusts to changes, and leverages opportunities is positioned to achieve enduring performance and a competitive edge.

Table 04: Dynamic Panel Estimation of Corporate governance factor on Firm performance (ROA) of whole Sample from 2007-2022

	Coef	Std Err.	Z	P>z
Return on Assets L1.	0.213480 (0.0000)	0.0001650	1294.260	0.000
Stock Return	1.0839460 (0.0000)	0.0058030	186.780	0.000
Ceo Experience	-0.319360 (0.0000)	0.0049580	-64.420	0.000
Market-value of Equity	0.0410570 (0.0000)	0.0005830	70.470	0.000
Leverage	-0.498050 (0.0000)	0.0006560	-759.680	0.000
Firm Age	0.2756270 (0.0000)	0.0044590	61.820	0.000

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) evaluates multicollinearity among independent variables in a regression model. Lower VIF levels (approaching 1) indicate little association. A VIF below 5 is generally considered appropriate, however numbers above 10 are concerning. In our examination: Leverage exhibits a VIF of 1.13, signifying little association with other variables.

The stock return has a VIF of 1.09, indicating a little connection. The expertise of the CEO and the age of the business demonstrate little collinearity, with a VIF of around 1.06. The market value of stock has an unusually low variance inflation factor of 1.02. The mean VIF for all variables is 1.07, indicating the lack of significant multicollinearity.

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Table 05: Variance Inflation Factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
Leverage	1.130	0.8867007
StockReturn	1.090	0.9142009
Ceo Experience	1.060	0.9471208
Firm Age	1.060	0.9477806
Market-value of Equity	1.020	0.9811710
Mean VIF	1.070	

(Arellano-Bond test) for zero autocorrelation in first-differenced errors

Table 06: Autocorrelation Test

Order	Z	Prob > z
1	-1.69840	0.08940
2	0.687060	0.49200

AB/GMM Examine for autocorrelation Iftikhar, K., & Azmat, S. (2024). The p-value obtained from the first-order autocorrelation test is 0.0894, indicating that statistical significance exists at a

level below 0.10. The results indicate that the null hypothesis of not having autocorrelation may be denied at a 10% significance level. The first-differenced errors demonstrate clear signs of first-

order autocorrelation. The p-value of 0.4920 from the second-order autocorrelation test above the significance level of 0.10. Therefore, we do not possess sufficient

evidence to reject the null hypothesis indicating the lack of second-order autocorrelation at a 10 per cent significance level.

Table 07: Sargan Test

chi2(117)	98.987052
Prob> chi2	0.88409

Source: Author Estimation Sargan Test, p > 5%*

The over identifying restriction (table 05) employed for identification using the Sargan test suggests that we are unable to dismiss the null hypothesis (H0: over identifying restrictions are valid) at the five percent significance level. This indicates a lack of adequate evidence to disprove the validity of the over identifying limitations.

The Sargan test demonstrates that there is no evidence to substantiate the claim that the instruments employed in the Instrumental Variable regression are faulty because of over identifying restrictions.

The outcomes of the Sargan tests and the second-order autocorrelation tests demonstrate that the dynamic estimators of the system GMM estimator possess resilience Iftikhar, K., & Azmat, S. (2024).

Conclusion and Policy Implications

The study seeks to ascertain the relationship between company performance, stock returns, firm size, firm complexity, and governance within the textile sector. company performance favourably influences stock return, return on assets, and company size, but leverage and corporate governance have negative impacts.

The performance of textile firms in Pakistan is influenced by the firm's size, stock return, complexities, and governance. A review of existing literature reveals a mixed relationship between CEO attributes and firm performance, indicating both positive and negative correlations. Resource dependence theory posits that firm performance is contingent upon external hiring, particularly experienced management. Numerous studies indicate that the experience of Chief Executive Officers (CEOs) can significantly enhance firm performance, as substantial experience enables the

avoidance of unavoidable challenges and the effective management of fraud and accounting scandals.

In this scenario, the CEO does not play a crucial role in the textile company; most CEOs are not externally recruited but are relatives or family members of the firm's owners. Consequently, their affiliation does not align with theoretical expectations. While stock returns significantly impact firm performance, firm age is regarded as a measure of complexity, reflecting the firm's strategic decision-making, functional adaptability, innovation in production, and comprehension of market trends and It is statistically significant, indicating a 27% impact on company performance. In the textile industry, significant decision-making is conducted by senior management, often the owner or a key stakeholder of the organisation.

The ability of businesses to conform to local and international legislation is made possible by rigorous compliance with governance standards, which in turn reduces the risk of situations involving legal issues. The presence of effective governance mechanisms helps to cultivate investor trust by ensuring that the company is managed in a manner that is congruent with the investors' best interests. Companies that demonstrate strong governance are more likely to attract investors from both the local and international markets, which makes it easier for them to have access to cash. In order to achieve greater operational efficiency, effective governance rules should be implemented. These policies should improve oversight and strategic decision-making. For governance frameworks to be effective, they must have thorough risk management procedures that

make it easier to identify and eliminate operational dangers. Not only can improved corporate governance in the textile industry help the performance of individual companies, but it also contributes to the overall economic stability and prosperity of Pakistan through its benefits.

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